

Succession Planning: A Panegyric Exploit

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Abstract: In today's world, succession planning has become a measure to sustaining the posterity of organisations; this line of thought has appealed to both the management of organisations and academia. This study aimed at examining succession planning and utilised a qualitative methodology; in addressing this aim, extant literature were reviewed in line with the evolution of succession planning, rationale for succession planning, challenges for succession planning, and the social exchange theory perspective to succession planning. The study also made recommendations and articulated the prospect for succession planning.

Keywords: Social exchange theory, Succession planning

I. Introduction

The reality of an organisation's death is an unspoken feature of an organisation's plan; the manifestation of this reality has more to do with the quality of the human resources available to an organisation, than any other resource. With a rapid increase in the global business landscape and unpredictable world event that has a ripple effect on organisation's operations, having a competent employee base that understands and proactively engages threats and exploits opportunities in the environment is the holy grail to sustaining a viable organisational posterity, hence, the preoccupation with succession planning (SP) by organisation's management.

SP is a human development strategy that aims to culture future leaders in organisations [1]. Organisations are rapidly advancing a culture of learning and development to improve their employee competence-base with the aim of gaining a competitive niche [2]. Luna [3] posits that SP is a long-term structured process of influencing goals and roles in an organisation and developing employee to undertake responsibilities competently. Rothwell [4] asserts that SP is significant to accomplishing core goals of an organisation, as it enables the organisation to meet target future needs by implementing strategic learning and development techniques and advancing high potential employees. The viable continuity and sustenance of organisations in recent times have become a significant quest for organisations that are conscious of their legitimacy and relevance to their stakeholders; this is mainly addressed through the scope of SP.

The present study utilised the social exchange theory, which captures employees' perceptions of social exchange relationships in their organisation, and explains the postulation that SP positively increases employees' behaviours (i.e. engagement and performance) [1, 5]. Hence, when organisations invest in their employees' training and development, employees reciprocate such social interaction by increasing their level of engagement and performance towards achieving an optimised (i.e. exercise discretionary effort) organisational goals.

Most organisation's claim to have a SP program [6], while this may have been a discussion point in a meeting, the active enactment and implementation of holistic SP policies and practices that influence an entire organisation's process is arguable. This study aims to examine the trajectory of SP qualitatively. The remaining section of this study addresses; the evolution of SP, the rationale for SP, challenges for SP, the social exchange theory perspective to SP, conclusion and prospect.

II. Evolution of Succession Planning

The trajectory of SP is reported to have been observed two thousand years ago, with the Roman armies who strategically replaced officers in the ranks [7], Fayol [8] posits that management is enshrined with the mandate of ensuring that offices and tasks are managed and carried out by the right employee; hence, an organisation's most treasured advantage is not just the employees, but the right employees (e.g. with the requisite skills and competences). This connotes that the sustainable posterity of organisations is anchored on employees who are committed to training, development, and driven to accomplish organisational goals.

Grusky [9] furthers the studies on SP; he proposed the rationale for SP and noted that SP is inevitable to accomplishing a positive organisational performance. The 1970s experienced an increased empirical and theoretical examination on SP, diverse aspects of the organisation were explored in relation to SP; leadership [10], demographics, career path, and organisation type [11]; an alignment in these variables increases the chances of succession. The 1980s, saw an exponential growth in SP concepts [12], this was mostly revealed in the areas of review and critique of literature; leadership succession [10], why succession occurred at different rates [13]. Notwithstanding this development, there was a need to explore new variables and processes in SP research. The late 1980s and early 1990s, experienced turbulence in the global business landscape, triggered a reactionary restructuring by organisations to survive [14, 15], this revealed the significant roles of non-management actors in decision-making and performance [16], hence, prompted scholars to examine SP practices that captured non-management actors in the organisation [17]. In the 2000s, SP was refined from the conventional practice of preparing employees (i.e. focus on top positions), Guinn [17]; Fulmer and Conger [18] propose that SP policies should be focused on raising leadership competencies across the different levels of the organisation. Fuller and Conger [18] observes that this calls for greater transparency in SP policies and practices, as against secrecy in its operations. SP is also observed to align talent retention, talent management, intellectual capital and human capital management, and they must be aligned with the organisational processes and culture [4, 17, 18].

Notwithstanding the academia and industrial interest in SP, transiting from theory to practice seems challenging [16]. Nonetheless, the revealing insight in the body of knowledge is gradually covering such challenging, although new challenges with changing times will inevitably exist.

III. Rationale for Succession Planning

In today's world, organisations are struggling to sustain their human resources and are mostly faced with two significant challenges; first the possible loss of experienced critical talent, and secondly, the shifting trends in the skilled market [19]. These challenges make SP and its execution a top priority for organisations competing in the talent market [20]. Evidently, the constant changes in the global business landscape and their effects are causing organisations to engage in SP practices proactively; the rationale behind this includes the following:

SP cushions the gap in key leadership positions with competent replacement [4]; it is an effective device for optimising human resources, leadership development and talent management for achieving organisational goals [21]. SP aids in saving external hiring cost and motivates internal employees to secure higher managerial positions [20]. Fink [22] posits that employees are interested in their career security and development; hence, the necessity for organisations to enact and execute strategies such as the SP to guarantee talent management. SP reduces the risk of employee turnover because of its proactive nature [20]. Appelbaum, Benyo, Gunkel, Ramadan, Sakkal and Wolff [23] posit that SP practices transfer the relevant organisational and work skill knowledge to the young generation who may assume managerial roles in the future.

Rothwell [24] posits that organisations that do not practice a formal SP program, face tougher challenges, i.e. finding the right employee for the right job, at the right time, increased employee turnover and de-motivation, key positions been replaced by external hiring, and such organisations may further face survival issues.

IV. Challenges for Succession Planning

While this study has given insight to the virtue in SP, Hirsh [25] acknowledges the recurring challenges of SP, which deals with fundamental issues and they include; the need to continually review and update SP policies and practices as situations in both the internal and external environment continuously evolve. Also, there is a need for analytical evaluation of people, skill, and their relevance for the organisation's future. Furthermore, the need to actively involve individual employees in the formation and implementation of SP policies and practices; most times, policies and practices are executed, which does not reflect the employee's expectations and reality. Guest and Mackenzie-David [26]

posit that the relatively secretive nature of SP practices may add suspicion of unfairness. Moreover, there is a need to broaden the scope of SP practices at all levels of the organisation and not just the top level. Finally, there is a need for active involvement and commitment of top-level management to the SP policies and practice program; SP policies and practices are not always given executive credence in reality.

V. Social Exchange Theory Perspective to Succession Planning

Social exchange theory (SET) is one of the significant conceptual paradigms for comprehending behaviours in the workplace [5]. Its evolution is visible from anthropology [27], sociology [28], and social psychology [29], with a focus on accessing types, mechanism, and results of social interactions [30]. SET covers social interactions (i.e. SP practices) within a system (i.e. organisation) that engage the exchange of significant resources (i.e. employee training, reward and compensation), create norms of trust (i.e. transparency), commitment (i.e. employee engagement) and expectation (i.e. job security, career advancement) that establish future exchanges [31, 32, 33].

SET articulates market and non-market social interactions and centres on the influence that norms of reciprocity, re-current interactions, and social structures possess in controlling social behaviour [30]. Tangible or intangible resources could be exchanged in the social interaction engagement; these resources could possess economic or socio-emotional value [5, 34]. Economic values denote financial needs, which are tangible [5]. Socio-emotional values denote employee's social and esteem needs, which are intangible [5].

SET evolves when employers truly care for employees, which triggers reciprocity from the employees [5]. Hence, the social exchange relationship is a mediating variable; beneficial and mutual exchange between strong relationships, and these relationships yield optimised work behaviour and productive employee attitudes [5].

VI. Conclusion, Recommendations, and Prospects

Having reviewed extant literature on this concept; the evolution of SP, the rationale for SP, challenges for SP, and the social exchange theory perspective to SP, it is critical to state that SP is significant to employee performance with a positive ripple effect on the organisation's performance. SP is an essential means through which organisations, which are conscious of their performance, advantages, and posterity achieve their end objectives. Based on the reviewed literature, it is clear that the application of SP policies and practices has a significant influence on the sustainable continuity of an organisation via developed employees' optimised competence.

To optimally explore the advantages in SP policies and practices, for achieving organisations objectives, the following recommendations should be executed: first, organisations should ensure adequate funding and support of SP policies and process. In addition, designers of SP requirements, policies and process should evaluate the organisational needs and forecast future needs. Also, transparency in the SP process and implementation should be promoted. Furthermore, SP practices should be actively supported by the management of the organisation. Finally, management should continuously evaluate SP to ensure that its requirements, policies, process, and practices are aligned with the present and future needs of the organisation.

The prospect for SP denotes a future where SP is seen as a competitive necessity; focused on enabling a seamless organisational development and transition of employees at all levels of the organisation. Organisations will articulate its long term vision, and critically observe the trajectory of threats and opportunities, with an aim at preparing employee to influence threats and exploit opportunities. Employees involved in this process are intrinsically influenced to reciprocate such organisational investment in their growth and development by optimising performance and exercising discretionary effort in accomplishing their tasks. The future of SP equips employees with an ownership structure mentality in carrying out their jobs. It enables employees with capabilities to stay focused on the vision of the organisation and making it a priority. Eventually, SP practices and policies will be custom-made for organisations that are committed to lead their industry and dictate the market pace; these will actualise when employees are actively involved in the holistic SP processes.

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Succession Planning: A Panegyric Exploit

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Succession Planning: A Panegyric Exploit

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